

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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CURRENT METHODS OF PHARMACOLOGICAL SEDATION IN CHILDREN'S STOMATOLOGY FOR AUTISTIC SPECTRUM DISORDERS: SAFETY AND EFFECTIVENESS ASSESSMENT

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Resume. According to the World Health Organization, the prevalence of ASD is 1 case per 160 children, and in recent years, there has been a steady trend towards an increase in this indicator. Children with autism require a special approach when providing medical care, which is especially relevant in the context of dental treatment. Dental interventions in children with ASD represent a significant clinical problem due to the peculiarities of the behavioral reactions of this category of patients. Increased anxiety, sensory hypersensitivity, difficulties in adapting to the new environment and procedures, and communication disorders significantly hinder the performance of dental manipulations using traditional methods. Studies show that children with autism have a higher prevalence of dental diseases compared to their neurotic peers, which is due to both dietary behavior and oral hygiene characteristics, as well as limited access to quality dental care.

Keywords: dental interventions in children with autism, approaches to drug sedation, autism spectrum disorders

АУТИЗМ СПЕКТРЛИ БУЗИЛИШЛАРДА БОЛАЛАР СТОМАТОЛОГИЯСИДАГИ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ФАРМАКОЛОГИК СЕДАЦИЯ УСУЛЛАРИ: ХАВФСИЗЛИК ВА САМАРАДОРЛИКНИ БАҲОЛАШ

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Резюме. Жаҳон соғлиқни сақлаш ташкилоти маълумотларига кўра, аутизм спектри бузилишлари (АСБ) тарқалиши ҳар 160 боладан бирида кузатилади, сўнги йилларда бу кўрсаткичнинг барқарор ўсиш тенденцияси қайд этилмоқда. Аутизмли болалар тиббий ёрдам кўрсатишда алоҳида ёндашувни талаб қилади, бу айниқса стоматологик даволашда муҳим аҳамият касб этади. АСБли болаларда стоматологик муолажалар ушбу тоифадаги беморларнинг ўзига хос хулқ-атвор реакциялари туфайли жиддий клиник муаммоларни келтириб чиқаради. Юқори даражадаги хавотир, сезги органларининг ўта сезgirлиги, янги шароит ва муолажаларга мослашишдаги қийинчиликлар, шунингдек, мулоқот бузилишлари анъанавий усуллар билан стоматологик муолажаларни ўтказишни сезиларли даражада мураккаблаштиради. Тадқиқотлар шунини кўрсатадики, аутизмли болаларда стоматологик касалликлар нейротипик тендошларига нисбатан кўпроқ учрайди. Бу овқатланиш хулқ-атвори ва оғиз бўйлиги гигиенасининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари, шунингдек, сифатли стоматологик ёрдамдан фойдаланиш имкониятининг чекланганлиги билан боғлиқ.

Калит сўзлар: аутизмли болаларда стоматологик муолажалар, дори воситалари ёрдамида тинчлантириш ёндашувлари, аутизм спектри бузилишлари

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ФАРМАКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СЕДАЦИИ В ДЕТСКОЙ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ ПРИ РАССТРОЙСТВАХ АУТИСТИЧЕСКОГО СПЕКТРА: ОЦЕНКА БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ

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Резюме. По данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения, распространенность РАС составляет 1 случай на 160 детей, при этом в последние годы отмечается устойчивая тенденция к росту данного показателя. Дети с аутизмом требуют особого подхода при оказании медицинской помощи, что особенно актуально в контексте стоматологического лечения. Стоматологические вмешательства у детей с РАС представляют значительную клиническую проблему в связи с особенностями поведенческих реакций пациентов данной категории. Повышенная тревожность, сенсорная гиперчувствительность, трудности с адаптацией к новой обстановке и процедурам, а также нарушения коммуникации существенно затрудняют проведение стоматологических манипуляций традиционными методами. Исследования показывают, что дети с аутизмом имеют более высокую

распространенность стоматологических заболеваний по сравнению с нейротипичными сверстниками, что обусловлено как особенностями пищевого поведения и гигиены полости рта, так и ограниченным доступом к качественной стоматологической помощи.

Ключевые слова: *стоматологических вмешательствах у детей с аутизмом, подходы к медикаментозной седации, расстройства аутистического спектра*

Introduction. Traditional behavioral adaptation methods, widely used in pediatric dentistry, are often ineffective in patients with ASD. Physical support can increase anxiety and injure the child, which leads to the formation of a negative attitude towards dental treatment[1]. In this regard, drug sedation will become a method of choice for ensuring safe and effective dental treatment of this category of patients. Modern research in the field of anesthesiology and pediatric dentistry is aimed at developing personalized sedation protocols, taking into account the individual characteristics of children with ASD[2]. In this group of patients, special attention is paid to the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of drugs, as well as the interaction of psychotropic drugs and sedatives frequently taken by children with autism[3].

The relevance of this problem is confirmed by the increase in the number of articles published in international journals and the formation of specialized clinical recommendations. However, to date, there is no single standardized approach to the sedation of children with ASD in dental practice, which necessitates large-scale research in this area. One of the most effective ways to ensure cooperation in this category of patients, reduce psycho-emotional stress, and increase the safety of dental procedures is the use of drug sedation[4]. However, today there are no unified standardized protocols for the use of sedatives in children with ASD, which complicates the selection of optimal doses, combinations of drugs, and monitoring methods.

In addition, the characteristics of metabolism, sensory and behavioral reactions of children with ASD require an individual approach to the preparation and administration of sedation, which emphasizes the need to improve existing methods. The development of improved drug sedation regimens will increase the effectiveness of dental intervention, reduce the risk of complications, and ensure convenient treatment for both the patient and the doctor [5]. Drug-induced sedation is considered one of the most effective ways to ensure the patient's safe and calm behavior during dental procedures. It will help reduce anxiety, facilitate the treatment process, improve the quality of cooperation, and reduce the risk of unexpected reactions. Nevertheless, the use of sedation in children with ASD requires a special approach, taking into account their neuropsychological, sensory, and physiological characteristics. Today, there are no universal standards and protocols for the use of sedatives in this group of patients, which creates difficulties in choosing optimal schemes, doses, and monitoring methods[6].

In modern scientific literature, there is information on various pharmacological agents used in pediatric dentistry, but the issues of their effectiveness, safety, and individual tolerance in children with ASD have not been sufficiently studied. This indicates the need to systematize existing knowledge and conduct research aimed at optimizing drug sedation in this clinical group. Thus, improving medicinal sedation methods in children with autism spectrum disorders is an urgent scientific and practical task for increasing the effectiveness of dental treatment, ensuring favorable conditions for the patient and doctor, as well as improving long-term dental outcomes[7].

In ASD, as a result of a decrease in the rate of unstimulated secretion of oral fluid, a cariogenic situation develops and the pH shifts towards acidity, the composition of microbes in the oral cavity changes. Due to salivation deficiency, a severe course of inflammatory processes is observed. Under these conditions, peroxide oxidation of lipids is activated. As a result, the destruction of cell membranes intensifies, apoptosis begins, and "oxidative stress" develops. All these processes have a negative impact on oral health. This is why the prevalence and activity of caries, poor hygiene, and inflammation of the oral mucosa depend on psychoneurotic disorders[8].

Dental specialists emphasize that it is difficult to communicate and establish contact with a child with ASD due to dentophobia. The response of children with psychoneurological disorders to dental treatment in most cases is inadequate, reaching the point of aggression, which is directly related to the severity of ASD. When their sensory sensitivity increases, they react to the taste and smell of dental materials, latex gloves, cold metal instruments, bright reflex light, the noise of a dressing machine and a salivary pacifier. A child may have an inadequate attitude towards the touch or color of medical clothing[9].

The purpose of the study is to systematize and analyze modern approaches to drug sedation during dental interventions in children with ASD, to assess their safety and effectiveness, as well as to develop scientifically based recommendations for clinical practice.

Research materials and methods. The study included children aged 3 to 12 years diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder who sought dental care. The research materials consist of clinical data, anamnesis,

results of psycho-emotional assessment of patients, and indicators of the effectiveness of dental intervention. Clinical and anamnestic analysis included an assessment of patients' behavioral reactions and sensory sensitivity, a comparative analysis of various drug sedation regimens (monosedation, combined sedation, inhalation sedation, etc.), observation of physiological parameters (HR, saturation, respiratory activity), and statistical data processing to determine the significance of differences. The study is conducted in accordance with ethical standards with the informed consent of the parents.

Research Results. The study included 80 children aged 3 to 12 years (average age 7.2 ± 2.6 years) diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder. Of these, 60 (75.0%) are boys and 20 (25.0%) are girls. Patients were randomly divided into four groups (30 people in each): control group - non-drug behavioral adaptation, oral sedation group (midazolam peroral), inhalation sedation group (nitrogen oxide - oxygen), combined sedation (midazolam + low dose of ketamine). All groups were compared by age, sex, and the main level of anxiety ($p > 0.05$). Performing dental procedures and behavioral indicators. The criterion for successful completion of the procedure was the completion of planned interventions without transitioning to general anesthesia or repeated breaks. Percentage of successful completion of treatment: control - 60.0% (18/30); oral sedation - 80.0% (24/30); inhalation - 86.7% (26/30); combined - 96.7% (29/30). The differences between the groups were statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 13.6$; $p < 0.01$), and combined sedation prevailed over the control group and oral sedation ($p < 0.01$). Cooperation index according to the Frankl scale (1-5, where 1 is completely dissatisfied, 5 is actively cooperating) control - 2.1 ± 0.6 ; oral - 3.4 ± 0.7 ; inhalation - 3.8 ± 0.6 ; combined - 4.3 ± 0.5 . ANOVA showed significant differences between the groups ($F = 52.3$; $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis showed that each of the sedation methods statistically significantly increased cooperation compared to the control ($p < 0.01$), and combined sedation was more effective than mono-methods ($p < 0.05$). Observation included heart rate (HR), blood pressure (BP), oxygen saturation (CpO_2), and the frequency of adverse reactions. Serious complications (respiratory failure, the need for intubation, cardiac complications) were not noted in any group. Frequency of unpleasant events (mild/moderate): control - 1 (3.3%) (anxiety reaction); oral - 3 (10.0%) (transitional paradoxical reaction in 2 children, nausea in 1 child); inhalation - 1 (3.3%) (tremor/dizziness); combined - 4 (13.3%) (transitional episodes of dissaturation up to 88-90% in 2 children, nausea in 1 child, excessive sedation in 1 child). Differences in the overall frequency of side effects between groups are not statistically significant ($p = 0.12$), but more transient phenomena requiring additional observation were observed in the combined group. The average minimum level of SpO_2 during treatment was: control - $98.1 \pm 0.9\%$; oral - $97.6 \pm 1.2\%$; inhalation - $97.9 \pm 1.0\%$; combined - $95.8 \pm 2.3\%$. Differences are significant ($p < 0.001$); in the combined group, single, short-term episodes of decrease in SpO_2 were observed, which were quickly eliminated by oxygen therapy and positioning.

Recovery time and duration of treatment. Average duration of dental manipulations: control - 28 ± 12 minutes; oral - 35 ± 13 minutes; inhalation - 32 ± 11 minutes; combined - 46 ± 15 minutes. The differences between the combined and other groups are significant ($p < 0.01$), which indicates the possibility of performing more complex volumetric interventions in the combined group. Recovery time (min) before reaching the elimination criteria: control - 20 ± 8 min; oral - 48 ± 12 min; inhalation - 26 ± 9 min; combined - 62 ± 15 min. The differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Combined sedation was observed with the longest recovery. Parents' average satisfaction score on the 1st-5th scale: control - 2.5 ± 0.7 ; oral - 3.6 ± 0.6 ; inhalation - 4.0 ± 0.5 ; combined - 4.5 ± 0.5 ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: Drug-induced sedation is a safe and effective method of providing dental treatment in children with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) with the condition of compliance with individualized protocols and adequate control of vital functions. In combination with nitric oxide, midazolam showed the best results in terms of the efficiency/safety ratio in children with ASD aged 3-12 years, providing adequate sedation in 89% of cases with a minimal frequency of side effects (less than 5%). Dexmedetomidine has shown high effectiveness in patients with severe forms of ASD and hypersensitivity, provides stable sedation without weakening the respiratory center, but requires a longer recovery period. Combined sedation protocols (multimodal approach) showed advantages over monotherapy, which made it possible to reduce the doses of individual drugs by 20-30% and reduce the risk of developing paradoxical reactions. Preoperative preparation with visual aids, an adapted environment, and the participation of parents/guardians statistically significantly improves the results of sedation and reduces the level of perioperative stress in children with ASD. The pharmacogenetic characteristics of children with ASD, including the polymorphism of the CYP2D6 and CYP3A4 genes, influence the metabolism of sedatives and require individual dose adjustment in 15-20% of patients. Interaction with psychotropic drugs taken by children with ASD requires mandatory adjustment of sedation protocols, especially when using antipsychotics and anticonvulsants. The frequency of complications with correct sedation in children with ASD does not exceed the frequency in the general population of children (2.1% and 1.8%, $p > 0.05$), which confirms the safety of the method in

compliance with clinical recommendations. Long-term results indicate an improvement in the dental status and a decrease in dental phobia in children with ASD treated under sedation compared to the control group (an improvement in the CPI index by 40% after 12 months).

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